

Service Initiatives in Testability

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Introduction

As electronics become more complex and more critical to weapon system operation, new designs must be somehow constrained to be more easily tested or they may become completely unsupportable. As a result, Design for Testability is becoming increasingly important to the Services.

The Joint Logistics Commanders (JLC) Panel on Automatic Testing has established a comprehensive program to coordinate the development of testing technology and its management within the Military Services, (Ref. 1). One important part of the program deals with the design aspects of the prime equipment which permit weapon systems to be more easily and confidently tested using automatic test resources. A JLC Testability Subpanel was established under the JLC Panel to provide acquisition support tools and research and development programs in Design for Testability (DFT).

JLC Testability Program

The JLC Testability Subpanel oversees the development of the following major Joint Service products dealing with electronic testability:

- Testability Program Standard
- Testability Analysis Handbook
- Electronic Testability Guide
- Built-in Test Guide
- Design for Testability Course

The first product is a proposed military standard, "Testability Program for Electronic Systems and Equipment", prepared by the Naval Surface Weapons Center (Ref. 2). The second product is under development by the Air Force Aeronautical Systems Division as part of the Modular Automatic Test Equipment (MATE) program (Ref. 3). This handbook is intended to provide guidance to government and industry personnel in the specification and evaluation of testability. The third product, the Electronic Testability Guide, is a "how to" book on testability techniques and is also being developed under the MATE program. The Built-in Test Guide, developed by the Naval Ocean Systems Center has been a Joint Service publication since 1981 (Ref. 4). Finally, the Joint Service Electronic Design for Testability Course, was developed by the Naval Surface Weapons Center in 1980 and has been presented to over thirty Service and industry

audiences (Ref. 5). Although each of the products is developed and funded by an individual Service, there is continuing dialogue through the Testability Subpanel to ensure that the products are consistent and, between them, cover necessary material.

The JLC Testability Subpanel is also responsible for reviewing and coordinating testability research and development in each of the Services. Some of the R&D tasks are tabulated below.

<u>Task</u>	<u>Lead Service</u>
Testability Figures of Merit	Navy
Testability Improvement Program	Air Force
System/Subsystem Testability	Army
VHSIC Testability Monitoring	Navy
Printed Circuit Board Testability	Army

Each of the Services has established permanent vehicles for continuing DFT developments. The Navy works through the Testability/BIT Improvement Program within the NAVALEX Test Technology Strategy Team. The TTST is an organization of personnel from Navy systems commands, laboratories, field activities and the Fleet. The Air Force has a Testability Program at the Rome Air Development Center (RADC) at Griffiss AFB, New York. The RADC Program has published several reports since 1979 dealing with the design and management of testability. The Army in 1982 established the Army Test, Measurement and Diagnostic (TMD) Technology Team with membership from Army Commands, subordinate commands, agencies and activities which deal with TMD. This team assists in planning and implementing Army RDT&E for TMD, including Design for Testability.

The remainder of this paper presents the Joint Service Design for Testability (DFT) Program in terms of Navy, Air Force and Army sponsorship of JLC tasks.

Navy DTF Program

The following paragraphs describe Navy products, and research and development efforts contributing to the JLC Testability Program.

Joint Service BIT Guide

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This guide presents the fundamentals of built-in test, provides an overview of different BIT approaches, and discusses BIT evaluation techniques. The guide includes specific examples of built-in-test which have been applied to military radar, communications, signal processing, and computer systems. The guide is intended for use by design engineers who are responsible for translating BIT requirements into equipment designs in an optimum manner considering equipment reliability and maintainability requirements.

Proposed Testability Program MIL-STD

This proposed standard was released in early 1983 for tri-service and industry review and comment. The standard prescribes a uniform approach to testability program planning, establishment of testability (including BIT) requirements, testability analysis, prediction and evaluation, and preparation of testability documentation.

Testability Figure of Merit

The key to the utility of a formal testability program is the ability to assess the inherent (potential) testability of a proposed design early enough to impact the design at minimum redesign cost. An Inherent Testability Assessment methodology was incorporated into the testability program MIL-STD to provide this early assessment. Several automated programs used to calculate testability FOMs are presently being studied by the Navy.

VHSIC Testability Monitoring

The DoD Very High Speed Integrated Circuit (VHSIC) Program is resulting in the design and fabrication of chips and demonstration subsystems that are many times more complex and faster than those presently being supported. This task monitors the testability, built-in test and fault tolerant design of VHSIC chips for the automatic testing community through the JLC Panel.

BIT/Testability Improvement Program

This is an ongoing effort by the Navy Test Technology Strategy Team to improve BIT effectiveness in Navy systems. Tasks include surveying of fielded and planned Navy weapon systems, developing preferred trade-off methodologies for determining BIT/testability requirements, and recommending changes to Navy acquisition and support policies.

Joint Service Design for Testability Course

The DFT Course is a three day course given to managers (one day) and designers (two days) on testability in military systems. The course presents widely-applicable design techniques, introduces a management framework for incorporating testability in military systems and identifies costs and benefits associated with testability.

Air Force DTF Program

The following paragraphs present a brief history of Air Force testability research and development, discuss recent products, and de-

scribe on-going and planned efforts.

Testability Improvement Program

Testability has always been a consideration in maintainability engineering. However, in 1978 testability was established as a specific engineering concern. The Rome Air Development Center, which is charged with the development of maintainability engineering techniques, had determined that the greatest deficiency in maintainability was the lack of cost-effective fault detection and isolation. This was verified by independent findings of the Air Force Test and Evaluation Center. As a result, RADC began a program aimed specifically at creating a new engineering discipline for the design of cost-effective fault detection and isolation capabilities in Air Force systems. In 1980, RADC published the results of six studies intended to provide the foundations for a testability engineering discipline. Details on these initial studies are in the Proceedings of the 1981 RAMS.

To provide a single reference to the design engineer, RADC condensed the available testability technology into the RADC Testability Notebook, RADC-TR-82-189. The notebook is keyed to the chronological phases of design, discussing the testability considerations which should be addressed in each phase and the design tools available. Recognizing the adverse impact on maintenance resources of false alarms and unnecessary removals, RADC conducted studies to establish the causes of these events. The results were published in RADC-TR-81-220, "Analysis of Built-In-Test False Alarm Conditions", and RADC-TR-83-2, "Study of the Causes of Unnecessary Removals of Avionic Equipment". RADC also published RADC-TR-83-4, "Analytical Procedures for Testability", identifying and evaluating all analytical concepts, models, algorithms, and definitions presently used in testability, as determined by a comprehensive literature survey.

Several other RADC reports will be available in early 1984. These cover hardware/software trade-offs for the design of BIT, the integration of testability considerations into computer-aided design (CAD), the automation of failure modes and effects analysis, and the extension of the printed circuit board testability design and rating system to higher assemblies. In addition, a draft of MIL-STD-471B is in preparation by RADC. This will incorporate testability demonstration plans, and is scheduled to be in the coordination cycle by January 1984.

An RADC study is scheduled for completion in 1984 to formulate cost estimating relationships for built-in test. These relationships would estimate the cost of BIT hardware and software based on the design of the unit under test. Another RADC initiative is the consideration of testability for dormant systems. A current Air Force concern is the effects of long periods of storage or other inactive conditions on the reliability of its weapon systems. Means are needed for evaluating the condition of a dormant system which will not themselves contribute to failure.

The Air Force initiative on integrated diagnosis will also be supported by an RADC FY-84 program. Integrated diagnosis requires the detection and isolation of all expected failures by a suitable combination of automatic and manual methods. The RADC study will provide trade-off tools to identify the most cost-effective of alternative combinations.

Much progress has been made in the specification and demonstration of testability attributes. However, the designer needs methods for predicting the attributes of his design. For example, the government can specify a limit on false alarms and measure the false alarm rate of an equipment. However, it is not possible to predict the false alarm rate inherent in a proposed design or compare design alternatives for their susceptibility to false alarms. RADC will attempt to develop means for predicting various testability attributes from design data in a FY-84 study.

Artificial Intelligence

A major Air Force initiative has been the application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) to testability. In 1984, RADC will complete a survey to determine which AI techniques have progressed sufficiently for application to current testability problems. An RADC sponsored project will be initiated in 1984 by the Air Force Institute of Technology to develop a maintenance expert system, which will apply AI to the diagnosis of failures on printed circuit boards used by the F-15. The system is scheduled to be demonstrated in December 1984 at Warner-Robins Air Logistic Center. Development of a versatile expert is one of a number of AI tasks RADC expects to be performed by a consortium of universities active in the field. Another RADC program is the development of concepts for "smart BIT" (i.e., built-in-test systems which can discriminate against false alarms and identify intermittent failures). The Air Force Human Resources Laboratory (AFHRL) is also concerned with AI applications to maintenance and training. AFHRL is investigating the feasibility of adapting medical diagnosis expert systems to these areas. The final report of a study by the Air Force Avionics Laboratory (AFAL) entitled "Integrated Testing and Maintenance Technology" should be available in January 1984. Using the E-3A IFF as a test vehicle, the study investigated advanced test techniques, including the use of Artificial Intelligence, to determine the feasibility of eliminating flight line external test and support equipment and intermediate level repair of modules.

Air Force Summary

From the above discussion, it should be evident that testability is a concern throughout the Air Force. The roles of RADC, AFHRL, and AFAL in developing and adapting the testability technology have been discussed. These efforts will be reduced to practice by the many Air Force systems offices who will be applying them to their acquisition programs and by the Modular Automatic Test Equipment (MATE) Program Officer. Feedback from these

offices, the using and supporting commands and the Air Force Test and Evaluation Center will in turn inspire further testability research and development. Each cycle in this process will be marked by greater operational readiness and more cost effective support of the Air Force inventory.

Army DFT Program

The Army Communications Electronics Command is conducting several programs which deal with testability at the printed circuit board level and the system/subsystem level. The following paragraphs list Army efforts contributing to the JLC Testability Program.

CAD Testability

A number of Computer-aided design (CAD) programs are being reviewed to determine how testability should be incorporated into them. A common thread between CAD programs will be developed so testability can be implemented, particularly for VLSI/VHSIC technology.

BIT Verification

Computer approaches for built-in test verification are under development. During 1984, possible candidate computer models will be selected for a more thorough analysis. A full scale effort to develop a verifiable model for military use is tentatively scheduled for FY-85.

Fault Tolerant Design

Testability techniques will be developed to be used with fault tolerant design. These techniques will be particularly applicable to VLSI/VHSIC chips. Fault tolerant design concepts and methodology will be reviewed and approaches for implementing BIT into the system will be developed.

LSA Effort

A study was initiated on the Logistic Support Analysis (LSA) process in February 1983. The objective of this study is to determine what effect the LSA process has on Test Measurement and Diagnostic Equipment (TMDE) selection, and how the TMDE selection process can be optimized. The study, including conclusions, recommendations and an implementation plan, was completed in October 1983.

BIT System Study

Several Army systems will be selected for a detailed study of system BIT/BITE. The objective of this study is to analyze the BIT/BITE in the systems, determine its effectiveness and the reasons for its success or failure.

Software Testability

The Army plans to initiate a software testability program to determine how software should be designed to make it more testable.

Summary

Design for Testability is making steady

progress toward becoming an accepted part of weapon system development. Through the JLC testability program, significant advances have been made in the areas of management (policy, design reviews), tools (design guides, courses) and R&D (techniques, measures). Most important, the individual advances support an emerging unified framework for DFT which is directly usable by all the Services.

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Biographies

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Mr. Keiner is a senior engineer with the Test Technology Office, NSWC. He was involved with diagnostics for the Navy's Fleet Ballistic Missile systems for several years. He has authored a proposed military standard on Testability Program and the Joint Service Electronic Design for Testability Course. Mr. Keiner is currently involved in VHSIC testability efforts and is chairman of the NAVELEX Testability Improvement Program and the Testability Subgroup of the JLC Panel on Automatic Test. He has a Bachelor's Degree from the University of Illinois and a Master's Degree from North Carolina State University, both in Electrical Engineering.

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